

PRIORITIES OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: this article brings information about the development of the financial market and the financial services sector, as well as reforms aimed at building a democratic society based on the market economy in our country.

Keywords: corporate securities, investment, Academy of banking and Finance, Finance Corporation, Stock Exchange.

It was noted that the Uzbek model in the development of economic development of our country was developed taking into account the social economic potential, the history of statehood of our people, national religious values and world experience. The dominance of the economy over politics, the importance of the chief reformer of the state, the rule of law a strong social policy, the gradual transition to a market economy this model, relying on the Famous Five Principles of a legal democratic state based on a market economy a reliable foundation of all practical work during the years of independence as a construction strategy, it became the driving force of progress.

As an important alternative to its traditional resource-based model in the effective development of the economy of our republic, the end-of-life results of technology and technology, science, as well as the continuous rise of the life of society in a holistic of particular importance is the transition to an innovative development strategy aimed at the effective use of human capital in order to ensure. Modern information technologies are suitable for an innovative and integrative social economy – an innovative development strategy that is flexible, dynamic, efficient, constantly updated, with new content and visibility. It also applies to the innovative and integrative development of industrial sectors, in particular modern ones.

Ensuring the competitiveness of our economy is one of the main pressing issues of sustainable development of our country in modern kung. The experience of the world's prominent Assoc and leading countries shows that structural transformation in order to achieve national social and economic reform can be achieved only by deepening, ensuring the rapid development of production networks in innovative and integrative and high-tech-based new industrial enterprises, modernizing operating capacities and accelerating innovative integrative modern technical renewal processes. In the world market, it is necessary to produce competing products in terms of price and quality.

Currently, the process of diversification of the production of national industrial products and modernization of its modern branches depends on the level of development of the material and technical base of economic activity of its subjects, since the effective use of the resource potential of enterprises is the prerequisites and main factor for ensuring economic growth and achieving stability.

It is not difficult to notice that today an outsourcing system is being introduced in many sectors of our economy. As an example of this, the lectures of the Security Council under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at an extended meeting said: "for the first time, an outsourcing system was introduced for the provision of Food For Troops. Outsourcing means that independent organizations, not the army itself, are now involved in preparing daily meals for military personnel. The organization of this work is entrusted to the authorities in the places. The introduction of such a system allows you to free personal content from tasks that are not inherent in it, focusing the entire energy of military personnel on improving their professional skills. We will definitely continue to work in this direction."

As a result of the reforms of the last five years, the necessary political-legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational foundations of the establishment of a new Uzbekistan were created in our country.

Systematic work has also been carried out to ensure human rights, strengthen the accountability and openness of public bodies and increase the political activity of civil society institutions, the role of the media, population and public associations. Strengthening the social protection of citizens and reducing poverty has been established as a priority of state policy, providing the population with new jobs and a guaranteed source of income, qualified medical and educational services, decent living conditions has reached a qualitatively new level.

The real sector of the economy and the financial market are experiencing difficulties in using the modern tools of the financial market to attract investment funds to enterprises due to developments. Through the penetration of households into the financial market, the issue of increasing their balance in the corporate securities market remains one of the pressing problems waiting for a solution.

The topic "urgent problems and prospects for the further development of the financial market and financial services sector: national practice and international experience" was discussed in a round table organized in cooperation with the committees of the Senate of the Supreme Assembly and the Academy of banking and finance. The problem of creating new jobs by introducing new types of financial management in the country with the participation of senators, Foreign and national experts, representatives of responsible ministries and departments, commercial banks was put in the middle.

The large-scale reforms carried out in Uzbekistan are aimed at building a democratic society based on a socially oriented market economy in the country, one of the main products of which is its market at a rapid pace.

The financial market includes the following segments:

- credit (capital of banks and other credit institutions, leasing) and deposits market;
- securities market;
- currency market;
- insurance and pension funds market, lottery game instrument market.

The Ministry of Finance of Uzbekistan has developed a draft concept for the development of the country's financial market in the medium and long term. The document was published on the portal of discussion of regulatory legal acts.

In Uzbekistan, a draft concept for the development of the financial market was developed in 2017-2021. The concept project for the development of the financial market was developed

by the Ministry of Finance of Uzbekistan in cooperation with the Korean Stock Exchange, UNDP, International Finance Corporation, the Institute of Forecasting and macroeconomic research under the Cabinet of Ministers and other structures.

From the above, we can conclude that a number of significant work is being carried out on the development of the financial market in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and we think that this will certainly pay off. In the near future, it will be difficult for us to observe the effect of these priorities.

The current day is marked by decrees, resolutions and laws being considered about our country and the large-scale reforms being carried out, as well as the fact that Uzbekistan is pursuing new milestones and our country has stepped to a new stage in its development, which in turn is aimed at increasing the well-being and living standards of the country's population.

References:

1. Akramovich N. A. THE PRIORITY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 185-191.
2. Хакимов О. М, Курбанов З. Х., Мухаммедов Ф. Реализация возможностей получения легких наполнителей на основе меньше пластиковых почв в нашей республике //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 176-181.
3. Мухтаров Б. А., Ортиков Ё. Ю. Культурное и экономическое развитие туризма в Узбекистане //Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 14. – С. 375-378.
4. Rashidov U., Rashidov A. Assessment of Costs For the Quality of Logistics Activities //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 39-43

